

A Comparative Analysis of the Coverage of the 2022 Russia law banning LGBTQ by TASS, BBC, CNN & Reuters

Every news outlet has a different approach on how they convey news articles to its audience. No two news organisations present in the same way when it comes to language, the choice of headlines, and the views presented. However, a good news article must address the 5Ws and H. According to Satini et al (2020, p. 39) in their journal article on the content analysis of News completeness elements, they stated that “the important information that concerns all the main elements of News are namely 5W and H”. They further explained that the manner in which the cogent information are compiled is relative on how the news delivery is done. In addition, Hartley claimed that one of the main purposes of the news in any medium is consistently to signal myths via everyday detail of newsworthy events in his book *Understanding News* (Hartley, 2014).

On November 24, 2022, the Lower House of the Russian Parliament passes a law banning LGBTQ and imposing substantial fines on anyone who promotes the non-traditional sexual relationship, popularly known as LGBTQ Propaganda. This development has drawn criticism and received considerable press coverage globally. This essay will look at four well-known news organisations with a global audience: the BBC (British Broadcasting Corporation), TASS (Russian News Agency), CNN (Cable News Network), and The Reuters. It will also critically analyse how each of the four news organisations covered the story, the news value in each report, and make comparisons and contrasts between the four journalistic reports.

To start with, a brief overview of each news outlets will be delved into, each organization’s news article delivery will be critically analysed before comparing and contrasting the four news organizations and highlighting their differences.

Russian News Agency (TASS) has been at the leadership board since 1904 which is over 113 years. It’s registered as a Federal State Unitary Enterprise owned by the Government of Russia. Repina et al (2018, p 558) in *Bis image of Russia* revealed that “in modern society mass media texts matched by a certain way, becomes one of the main sources of stereotypes”. TASS is been realised to be greatly influenced by the government leadership.

In March 2022, Reuters removed TASS Russian News agency from its content marketplace. This happened because there were criticisms on how Russia's state owned news agency was portraying the war in Ukraine. It was believed that "TASS content available on Reuters connect was not aligned with the Trust principles which was to act with integrity, independence and freedom from bias". Around same time, Getty Image stated their ending of the partnership with a Russian News Agency, TASS because of what they called "violating editorial policy". These have brought lots of concerns over the leadership influence on TASS news agency.

CNN and Reuters are privately owned news organisations that are renowned for their international audience and global circulation of news content. Both being private media outlet and in terms of how they report their news can be explained using the liberal model of media system (Hallin & Maldini, 2004). The mass-circulation press as well as the early growth of press freedom are characteristics of this. With the notable exception of the very partisan British press, commercial media predominate, there is little political parallelism, as well as internal pluralism is the norm.

In terms of its style of reporting news, many research has been made into whether CNN style of reporting is devoid of its ownership influence. Jung and Kim (2011, p 71-79) were also not left out in this research work. They examined whether CNN, one of the most popular cable TV news channels in the U.S showed a favourable bias in the covering Time Warner's movie product which eventual revealed that "in spite of the poor performance of Time Warner movies, CNN covered more news about Warner Brothers and other subsidiary producing movies for Time Warner." They also revealed that "CNN showed favoritism toward its parent company's movie studio in terms of the quantity in news coverage. Therefore, ownership likely has an influence on media content."

The primary public broadcaster in the UK is the BBC. The Royal Charter of the organisation lays out its goals, obligations, and rules for governance (Boaden, 2014). The BBC offers a broad range of television, radio, and online services, and its aim is to inform, educate, and entertain. According to its charter, the BBC has five public objectives, namely reporting the news objectively and representing the UK, her culture, and its values abroad. Although funded by the Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport (DCMS) and overseen by Ofcom, the communications

regulator, the BBC is independent of the government (Boaden, 2014). According to its charter, the BBC must remain independent of political and commercial sway and answer exclusively to the people who watch and listen to it. Despite the fact that this political objectivity is occasionally disputed. According to Hallin & Mancini's (2004) model of media and politics, this is a clear indication that the BBC falls under the democratic media model.

The liberal principles that the two media outlets (CNN and Reuters) include in their articles is a big part of why they have a global reach. Also, because of the low level of political and governmental involvement in its news production (Brüggemann et al., 2014). Unlike the Russian News Agency (TASS), which strictly speaks about the approved laws by the State Duma with fines attached to breaking the laws and nothing about the LGBT people, other human rights activists, or the world's view about the law.

To start with, I would analyse the four outlets headlines of their stories. According to Tannenbaum (1953), it emphasizes the role of the headline in everyday news media to a reading behavior. The CNN article begins with the headline "Russia's State Duma approves bill to ban 'LGBT propaganda'," (Appendix One), Reuters headline says "Russian parliament passes law banning 'LGBT propaganda' among adults" (Appendix Two), and BBC headline states "Russia passes 'Answer to Blinken' gay propaganda law" (Appendix Three), these immediately establish that Russia passed a law that bans the LGBT propaganda. Furthermore, the three above news media were more interested in the LGBT community in their headlines. This discretion is not used by TASS in their article, who begin with the headline "State Duma approves law on fines for LGBT, pedophilia, gender reassignment propaganda" (Appendix Four). This title does provide a clear and thorough message that the Russian government is against the LGBT propaganda. Additionally, TASS headline does not focus on LGBT but also on pedophilia and other gender reassignment propaganda.

The first sentence of the BBC (British Broadcasting Corporation) story goes on to explain that the new law might be dangerous, carries a severe penalty, and that the Russian parliament's lower chamber chose it. Making reference to the law as the "Answer to Blinken" law, this is essentially a response to US Secretary of State

Antony Blinken's criticism of it as a "blow to freedom of expression." Such wording can have a profound effect on readers' perceptions. While TASS continues to report on the intricacies of the law revisions and goes as far as defining what propaganda means in the context of the law, which Oates (2017) refers to when calling Russian media as merely "political players" in obedience to the political authority existing, there is still no reference of the Blinken law in the opening two paragraphs of the TASS piece as there was from the BBC. Consequently, the increasingly powerful political leadership "not tolerates" (Oates, 2017, p. 1285) any effort at independence from political alignment. This degree of bias in the press may have its roots in the nation's Soviet past, when "party subordinated ideologised journalism" (Kiriya, 2019, p. 17) and a significant engagement from the Communist leadership at the time have persisted and led to an unusual amount of media distortion and prejudice.

The European Court of Human Rights' 2017 decision, which denounces Russia's purported "gay propaganda law" as an infringement of the European Convention on Human Rights, is discussed in the opening paragraph of the CNN story. This demonstrates why CNN is a liberal media outlet and inadvertently draws attention to the nation's harsh treatment of a particular group of people. CNN can also be regarded to be making enormous achievements in the area of global journalism, despite the claims made by certain studies that their quick technique to news results obtained in a watered-down knowledge of international news (Berglez, 2008). Storytelling that goes beyond simply covering events in other nations is referred to as "global journalism," which makes sure that the story is placed in a larger, global context (Berglez, 2008). In general, CNN's stance on the story is consistent with its broad approach to journalism.

Conversely, Reuters news media which also highlights the effect of the new law which makes LGBT lifestyle almost impossible in Russia in its first two paragraphs started with a video. This 2min 40secs video showed various LGBT protesters being arrested and maltreated by the Russian police force. The article went on to explain how the law was targetted at children before it is been rebranded to target adults too. It further highlights how the "Russian world" is constantly against a liberal western countries and its policies. This is put the new law into a global context which can then be accurately branded as global journalism. This is in contrast to what we can see

in the article of Russian News Agency (TASS) which specifies more about the law and the fines, which shows that the new media is more politically inclined, and that the state plays a large role as an owner, regulator, and funder of this media, though its capacity to regulate effectively is often limited.

The two main themes of the TASS story are a lack of human rights and poor empathy. The main stream media current function in Russia is "attempting to manipulate content, rendering it loyal" (Kiriya, 2019), demonstrating not just that facts are being ignored but also that the overwhelming majority of major media users are essentially subject to countries control. There is little indication of incorporation or variation in the TASS item, which simply portrays the opinions of Russians. Global media must "integrate" (Berglez, 2008) individuals, places, and practises. The Reuter's, on the other hand hand, adheres to Berglez's ideas of global journalism throughout their article by utilising a wide range of sources.

Because this event meets a number of requirements, it has garnered widespread attention and been extensively covered by the BBC, CNN, and Reuters. This news item's unfavourable tone and mention of a Russian's penalty for LGBT propaganda are two factors. In comparison to the consequences of positive news, the perception of negative news is much more "consensual" (Galtung & Ruge, 1965). This is because more people concur that the impact of negative news are negative. Negative stories fills "latent" (Galtung & Ruge, 1965) consumer demands, which is why both channels report it. The event is quite newsworthy and meets several of the criteria outlined by Harcup and O'Neill (2017) for media coverage. The story according to TASS fulfils the concerns that Russia have on the issues of LGBT propaganda and the moral standards of the country. However, to the western world, the story as highlighted by CNN, BBC and Reuters portrays the negative impact of the Russian LGBT laws on the general human rights.

The BBC story is also more concerned with the overall impact of the Russian law on LGBT people because it emphasises that the victims are not all Russian citizens. The article makes similar allusions to global Human Rights campaigners. The story, however, becomes one-sided as a result of the story's overwhelming focus on the LGBT victims since it communicates an attitude that disregards the sovereignty of the Russian state. Similar to this, the usage of Tweets from Secretary Anthony Blinken

emphasises the article's worldwide perspective. Although Vyacheslav Volodin, the Speaker of the Duma, provided his perspective in the story, it is clear from the placement of the violation of human rights by the Russian Parliament at the article's top that the BBC, CNN, and even Reuter have a liberal bias. Evidently, the CNN, BBC, and Reuters pieces have a more global perspective than the TASS ones, which take a more domestic and political-focused stance.

It is possible to compare and contrast the LGBT stories in each article in terms of what has been thought to be newsworthy. Harcup & O'Neill (2001) argued that news values might be broken down into ten different categories, in a thorough study of a plethora of empirical studies. For the BBC, CNN, and Reuters news media outlets, the primary LGBT propaganda meets the news value criteria of "Bad news" and "Magnitude," but it doesn't appear to do so for the TASS news media outlet. Any major news organisation would find a story on LGBT people noteworthy because such human rights propaganda would typically elicit universal sympathy, irrespective of political or ownership goals. The video selection in Reuters is comparable to that in CNN, showing the rights of LGBT activists and protesters being infringed upon. The images in Reuters and the BBC also highlight the symbol and support for the LGBT community, but the same cannot be said of the TASS, which only displays a picture of the Lower house of parliament.

Images from publications by CNN, BBC, and Reuters clearly show individuals holding LGBT pride flags in solidarity of the group; one image depicts a young man who has been brutally attacked being held up by two women. Current follow-up research by Harcup & O'Neill (2017), that gives a slightly modified list of media ethics established in the face of the emergence of online-based news and social media, may have influenced the choice to include images of the bereaved supporters. According to their meta-analysis, which concentrated on the elements of online news that produce a large number of article views, strong visuals were identified as a crucial component of 21st-century online news.

Even while the articles may have different principles, it is possible to discern that they diverge in regards to the organisations' news agendas, which is yet another news value cited by Harcup & O'Neill (2017). The mission of CNN and Reuters seems to be rather benign, with the emphasis on offering a fair, comprehensive mix of news from throughout the world rather than pushing a particular purpose. On the other hand, the

TASS's support for the Russian government is evident in all of its reportage. The law enacted by the Russian government and the associated fine are being emphasised in this case. Of course, in this particular circumstance, the CNN, BBC, and Reuters goals might not be overtly political. However, their use of the chance to provide a particular derogatory opinion on the Russian statute supporting the LGBT population as if it were the only nation to do so might be regarded as unethical in the field of journalism.

My critical examination of CNN, BBC, Reuters, and TASS has revealed significant disparities in how they portray the LGBT propaganda narrative and how they operate within the larger field of international journalism. The BBC operates in a democracy free from government meddling. The approaches to international journalism taken by CNN and Reuters are more liberal. Apparently, TASS is biased because it is primarily from a Russian perspective and aims to protect the interests of Russia. The articles by CNN, BBC, and Reuters appear to be more impartial and comprehensive in their journalistic coverage of the LGBT propaganda in Russia. They give different perspectives and consistently adhere to the human rights perspective while avoiding subjective writing. In a country where media freedom and openness are highly impacted by the Polarized Pluralist model, TASS is still in operation. Therefore, the context has a big impact on their coverage.

However, omitting to connect the LGBT propaganda to numerous other nations that are also supporting the same propaganda limits its capacity to be dubbed "global journalism." It was discovered that CNN, BBC, and Reuters generally maintained their position as a leader in international media. It was discovered that the TASS piece mostly concentrated on internal issues and made few allusions to the crisis in a global context. The polarised pluralist component in the comparison of the four articles was discovered to be the news agency owner agenda of the TASS.

References

- Berglez, P. (2008). WHAT IS GLOBAL JOURNALISM? *Journalism Studies*, 9(6), 845–858. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616700802337727>
- Boaden, H. (2019). *NewsWatch | About BBC News | This is BBC News*. Bbc.co.uk. http://news.bbc.co.uk/newswatch/ukfs/hi/newsid_3970000/newsid_3975900/3975913.stm
- Brüggemann, M., Engesser, S., Büchel, F., Humprecht, E., & Castro, L. (2014). Hallin and Mancini Revisited: Four Empirical Types of Western Media Systems. *Journal of Communication*, 64(6), 1037–1065. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12127>
- Galtung, J., & Ruge, M. H. (1965). The Structure of Foreign News. *Journal of Peace Research*, 2(1), 64–90. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002234336500200104>
- Hallin, D. C., & Mancini, P. (2004). *Comparing Media Systems : Three Models of Media and Politics*. Cambridge University Press, Dr.
- Harcup, T., & O’Neill, D. (2017). What is News? *Journalism Studies*, 18(12), 1470–1488. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1461670X.2016.1150193>
- Hartley, J. (2014). *Understanding news*. Routledge.
- Jung, J., & Kim, H. (2010). A Clash of Ownership and Journalism: CNN’S Movie Coverage. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1718135>
- Kiriya, I. (2019). New and old institutions within the Russian media system. *Russian Journal of Communication*, 11(1), 6–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19409419.2019.1569551>
- Oates, S. (2007). The neo-Soviet model of the media. *Europe-Asia Studies*, 59(8), 1279–1297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09668130701655150>
- Satini, R., Tatalia, R. G., & Rahmat, W. (2020). CONTENT ANALYSIS OF NEWS COMPLETENESS ELEMENTS TEXT FOR STUDENTS OF SMP NEGERI 24 PADANG. *Journal of Asian Studies: Culture, Language, Art and Communications*, 1(1), 38–44. <https://doi.org/10.51817/jas.v1i1.5>
- Tannenbaum, P. H. (1953). The Effect of Headlines on the Interpretation of News Stories. *Journalism Quarterly*, 30(2), 189–197. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769905303000206>

Appendix 1

<https://edition.cnn.com/2022/11/24/europe/russia-lgbt-propaganda-law-amendment-intl/index.html>

Appendix 2

<https://www.reuters.com/world/russias-parliament-passes-law-banning-lgbt-propaganda-among-adults-2022-11-24/>

Appendix 3

<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-63747732>